

PARTICIPATION IN PEACE OPERATIONS AS A FOREIGN POLICY TOOL AFTER THE INTERNATIONAL FORCES' WITHDRAWAL FROM AFGHANISTAN: A COMPARISON BETWEEN ITALY AND BULGARIA

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Introduction

Peace operations have a significant role in achieving and preserving international peace and security. They are also an essential part of many countries' foreign policy. As Bellamy and Williams (2012, p. 3) argue, the reasons behind a state's decision to contribute to peace operations can be generally narrowed to politically, economically, security, institutional and normative driven ones.

Therefore, the international forces' withdrawal from Afghanistan has led to a reconsideration of foreign policies across many countries for which that was a theater of prime importance. This paper compares and analyze the choices made by Bulgaria and Italy in the aftermath. It argues that avoiding to actively participate in peace operations leads to weakening and losing of capacity, including in economic terms, which can transform into security gaps and political hardship at the national level.

Methods

This article is based on a comparison between Italy and Bulgaria, taking into account the following indicators:

- political and economic reasons for participation in peace operations, including trade relations with third countries;
- defence expenditures and peace operations' costs over the last two decades;
- changes in the state policy towards peace operations after the Taliban overthrow in Afghanistan in 2021;
- participation in current peace operations and number and type of personnel deployed.

The study is limited to peace operations led by international organizations and conducted in (post)conflict areas. Therefore, other military operations, even if of a non-combat character, fall outside of the study's scope.

Results

The withdrawal from Afghanistan can be seen from various perspectives: from the vast resources spent on such interventions at the background of unclear results and constant budgetary competition in the contributing countries, to the possibility of redirecting resources to other important theaters of action.

The comparison between Bulgaria and Italy gives useful insights on how two EU and NATO members that face similar security threats, regard peace operations differently, including from an economic perspective, leading to security gaps and challenges.

The paper also indicates that participating in peace operations for predominantly limited security and political reasons only, as in the case of some EU countries (e.g. Konečná, 2021, pp. 306-311; Pedersen, 2020, pp. 11-16), may also lead to security gaps while missing important economic aspects.

References

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